

Hysteroscopic Resection of a Cervical Ectopic Pregnancy: Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Cervical ectopic pregnancy (CEP) is a rare form of ectopic pregnancy, accounting for less than 1% of all ectopic pregnancies, with an estimated incidence of 1 in 9,000 pregnancies. Historically, the management of CEP has involved hysterectomy due to the high risk of uncontrolled hemorrhage. However, advancements in early diagnosis through high-resolution ultrasound and serum beta-human chorionic gonadotropin (β -hCG) quantification have allowed for the exploration of conservative management approaches aimed at preserving fertility.

Case Presentation: We present the case of a 25-year-old female, with no significant gynecological or obstetric history, who presented to the emergency department with vaginal bleeding. Ultrasound examination revealed a gestational sac located in the endocervical region, without a visible embryo, and β -hCG levels were 4,436 mUI/mL. Medical management with methotrexate was initiated according to a multiple-dose regimen, supplemented with folinic acid, but did not result in adequate resolution. Given the persistent rise in β -hCG levels (8,225 mUI/mL), surgical intervention via hysteroscopy was performed. Under regional anesthesia, hysteroscopic resection of the gestational sac was successfully completed using bipolar energy, achieving effective hemostasis with minimal blood loss (50 mL). The patient had an uneventful recovery and was discharged after 72 hours. Follow-up at three weeks post-procedure showed a decrease in β -hCG to undetectable levels (2.3 mUI/mL).

Conclusion: Hysteroscopic resection is a safe and effective conservative treatment option for cervical ectopic pregnancy, minimizing surgical morbidity, preserving fertility, and avoiding radical interventions. However, this approach requires specialized expertise and careful patient selection. Standardized clinical protocols are needed to optimize outcomes and reduce complications.

KEYWORDS: Cervical ectopic pregnancy, Operative hysteroscopy.

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INTRODUCTION

The blastocyst normally implants in the endometrial lining of the uterine cavity. Implantation elsewhere is considered ectopic and accounts for 0.5% to 1.5% of all first-trimester pregnancies. Approximately 95% of ectopic pregnancies implant in various segments of the fallopian tube. The ampulla (70%) is the most common site, followed by isthmic (12%), fimbrial (11%), and interstitial (2%) pregnancies. The remaining 5% of ectopic pregnancies implant in the ovary,

peritoneal cavity, a previous cesarean section scar, or the cervix.¹

Cervical ectopic pregnancy is a rare form of ectopic pregnancy in which implantation occurs in the lining of the endocervical canal. This condition accounts for less than 1% of ectopic pregnancies. The incidence is approximately 1 in 9,000 pregnancies.^{1,2}

Predisposing factors for cervical ectopic pregnancy include endometrial damage from previous scarring or surgeries,

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uterine curettage, chronic infections, intrauterine device (IUD) use, and pregnancy. More recently, an increased frequency has been associated with pregnancies achieved through in vitro fertilization and embryo transfer.³

The general approach to evaluating a suspected ectopic pregnancy includes medical history, physical examination, serum human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG), and transvaginal ultrasound.^{2,3}

Ultrasound criteria for diagnosing a cervical pregnancy include:⁴

- Gestational sac within the cervix
- No evidence of intrauterine pregnancy
- Visualization of an endometrial stripe
- Hourglass-shaped uterus with a dilated cervical canal
- Closed internal cervical os

Treatment for these cases almost always involves hysterectomy due to uncontrollable bleeding or as the treatment of choice, accounting for up to 70% of cases. However, the measurement of beta subunit human chorionic gonadotropin (β -hCG) and improved ultrasound resolution have led to the development of multiple conservative treatments that reduce morbidity and preserve fertility.⁵

Several case reports in which cervical ectopic pregnancy has been diagnosed via ultrasound have described the use of methotrexate at a dose of 1 mg/kg/day on days 1, 3, 5, and 7, with folinic acid rescue therapy on days 2, 4, 6, and 8; with a maximum of four doses, achieving positive results in evacuating the ectopic pregnancy. However, there are also

reported cases in which additional procedures such as electrocoagulation via hysteroscopy or aspiration curettage were necessary despite this treatment.⁶

The aim of this article is to describe the successful treatment of a cervical ectopic pregnancy through hysteroscopic resection.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 25-year-old female, originally from and residing in Ticul, Yucatán, with no significant family medical history. She denies substance abuse. She has a history of cesarean section three years ago due to persistent fetal tachycardia, resulting in a full-term newborn without complications. No other relevant personal pathological history. Menarche at age 11, regular menstrual cycles, no use of family planning methods, and a cervical cytology performed one year ago showed no abnormalities.

She presented to the obstetric emergency department for evaluation due to reported transvaginal bleeding. Upon examination, the patient was hemodynamically stable with no active transvaginal bleeding. A urine pregnancy test was performed and returned positive, prompting a request for quantitative human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG), which reported a level of 4,436 mIU/mL. A transvaginal ultrasound was requested, which showed a uterine cavity with an endometrial thickness of 12 mm and a 17.2 mm gestational sac, without a visible embryo but with a clearly defined yolk sac located in the endocervical region (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Cervical implantation gestational sac.

Hospital admission was decided, and medical treatment with methotrexate at a dose of 1 mg/kg/day was initiated on days 1, 3, 5, and 7, with biochemical monitoring for adverse effects of the drug. Folinic acid rescue therapy was administered on days 2, 4, 6, and 8. A new hCG quantification showed a level of 8,225 mIU/mL. Since hCG levels persisted and continued to rise, surgical resolution via hysteroscopy was decided.

Under epidural anesthesia, a diagnostic hysteroscopy was first performed using the vaginoscopy technique with a 3.2

mm Betchi hysteroscope, using 0.9% saline solution infused with a Hamou II Endomat pump at a pressure of 80 mmHg and a flow of 100 mL per minute. The procedure began with observation of a dilated external cervical os and a gestational sac implanted on the posterolateral right wall of the endocervical canal. Patent tubal ostia and an unoccupied uterine cavity were observed (see Figures 2 and 3).

Figure 2. Implantation of the gestational sac on the posterolateral endocervical surface.

Figure 3. Panoramic view of the uterine cavity. The cervical implantation site, empty uterine cavity, and patent ostia are observed.

Subsequently, a surgical hysteroscopy was performed using an 18.5 French Strauss resectoscope with bipolar plasma energy from a Gyrus ACMI PK Superpulse G400 generator. Coagulation of the gestational sac implantation site was initiated, followed by cutting energy and complete excision. Hemostasis was confirmed, and the procedure was completed without complications. The estimated postoperative blood loss was 50 mL. The patient remained stable and was monitored in the hospital for 72 hours, after which she was discharged and followed up in outpatient consultation three weeks later. At follow-up, her human chorionic gonadotropin level was 2.3 mIU/dL.

DISCUSSION

Cervical ectopic pregnancy is associated with massive hemorrhage, and the most common treatment is hysterectomy. However, measurement of β -subunit human chorionic gonadotropin (β -hCG) and improved ultrasound resolution have led to the development of multiple conservative treatments that reduce morbidity and preserve fertility, provided the patient is hemodynamically stable.⁷ In our patient, the diagnosis of cervical ectopic pregnancy was confirmed by quantitative hCG testing and the identification of a gestational sac located in the endocervical canal via transvaginal ultrasound. Since the patient was hemodynamically stable and in good general condition, we were able to offer her an initial conservative treatment.

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Standardized treatment options include systemic methotrexate, local intra-gestational injection of methotrexate or potassium chloride, dilation and curettage, uterine artery embolization, and hysterectomy. A combination of methods is often required.⁸

Hysteroscopy is an endoscopic exploratory technique used to examine the interior of the uterine cavity and endocervical canal. It can serve both diagnostic and therapeutic purposes, including various minor surgical procedures, which are generally well tolerated by most patients. It is considered a simple, safe, and highly effective procedure.⁹ Numerous successful cases of hysteroscopic resolution of cervical ectopic pregnancies as a sole treatment have been published. Rojas and Chacha reported a case of cervical ectopic pregnancy successfully treated with minimal bleeding using bipolar surgical hysteroscopic ablation.¹⁰ Similarly, López Ortiz et al. published a retrospective study of a series of cervical ectopic pregnancy cases treated at the Hospital Español de México between 2002 and 2016, where hysteroscopic management with bipolar energy was used as initial treatment. All seven patients had satisfactory outcomes, minimal bleeding, and fertility preservation.¹¹

In our case, however, hysteroscopic treatment was not the first-line option. We initially chose medical management with methotrexate due to its lower invasiveness. However, due to treatment failure and rising β -hCG levels, we opted for a diagnostic hysteroscopy to localize the exact implantation site of the ectopic pregnancy, followed by surgical resection using bipolar energy. The results were excellent and free of complications.

Alanis-Fuentes and colleagues also reported a case of a cervical ectopic pregnancy in which medical treatment with methotrexate was initially offered. After treatment failure, surgical hysteroscopic resolution with bipolar energy was performed, resulting in effective treatment with minimal bleeding and no complications. A hysterosalpingography performed three months later showed a normal cervical canal, uterus, and fallopian tube pathways.¹² This case was comparable to ours, where hysteroscopy was used after failure of medical treatment, yielding equally satisfactory results.

Despite these successful reports, there is currently limited scientific evidence supporting the use of hysteroscopy as a conservative treatment for cervical ectopic pregnancy.¹¹ Most published studies are isolated case reports, highlighting the need for further research to establish more standardized protocols and guide clinical practice. Conservative management via hysteroscopy, while promising, requires highly trained personnel and experience to ensure effectiveness and minimize risks.

CONCLUSION

Hysteroscopic resection represents an effective and safe therapeutic alternative for the conservative management of cervical ectopic pregnancy in selected patients. This approach

minimizes surgical morbidity, preserves fertility, and avoids radical interventions. However, its implementation requires specialized expertise and careful individualized assessment. The need to standardize clinical protocols is emphasized in order to optimize outcomes and reduce complications.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS: This article does not involve human subjects or the use of patient data; therefore, informed consent was not required. Similarly, as there was no intervention, manipulation, or handling of information, the study was considered low-risk and did not require review or approval by the local ethics committee. Nevertheless, it complies with current research regulations, and the confidentiality of identifying and personal data, as well as the anonymity of participants (all healthcare workers who participated voluntarily), are guaranteed. This article does not contain personal information that could identify the participants.

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